

GALACTIC REDSHIFTS

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ABSTRACT

A previously predicted electromagnetic time dilation effect has been shown to correctly predict decay lifetimes of muons bound to atomic nuclei. It has also been shown that the electromagnetic time dilation, along with the gravitational time dilation can produce total redshifts of $z = 4.89$ for a neutron star with a magnetic field of $B \sim 1.25 \times 10^{13}$ G. Also, $z = \infty$ or cutoff for a neutron star with a magnetic field of $B \sim 1.87 \times 10^{13}$ G. In this paper we first show that the redshift of a neutron star can reach $z = 10.1$ for $B \sim 1.53 \times 10^{13}$ G. This is the redshift of UHZ1, which is breaking current models. Then we show that for a galaxy redshifts can reach $z = 14.32$ when the emitter is in a localized magnetic field of $B \sim 3.13 \times 10^{13}$. For this model all other radiation is assumed to be a reflection. This is the redshift of JADES-GS-z14-0, which is also breaking current models. We then show that the electromagnetic redshift explains the unusually narrow spectral lines of JADES-GS-z14-0.

KEY WORDS: General relativity; Electromagnetic field; Galaxy; Redshifts; Quasars

1. INTRODUCTION

A previously predicted electromagnetic time dilation effect [1] has been shown to correctly predict decay lifetimes of muons bound to atomic nuclei. [2] It has also been shown that the electromagnetic time dilation, along with the gravitational time dilation can produce total redshifts of $z = 4.89$ for a neutron star with a magnetic field of $B \sim 1.25 \times 10^{13}$ G. We get $z = \infty$ or cutoff for a neutron star with a magnetic field of $B \sim 1.87 \times 10^{13}$ G. [3] In this paper first we show that for neutron stars $z = 10.1$ for $B \sim 1.53 \times 10^{13}$ G. This is the redshift of UHZ1, which is breaking current models. [7] Then we show that for a galaxy redshifts can reach $z = 14.32$ when the emitter is in a localized magnetic field of $B \sim 3.13 \times 10^{13}$. For this model all other radiation is assumed to be a reflection. This is the redshift of JADES-GS-z14-0, which is also breaking current models. [5] We then show that the electromagnetic redshift explains the unusually narrow spectral lines of JADES-GS-z14-0.

2. REDSHIFTS

Let us assume a neutron star is a uniform spherical mass with an emitting surface. A galaxy can have very strong localized magnetic fields with magnetars and neutron stars. So let us assume that a galaxy is a uniform spherical mass with an emitting surface in a localized magnetic field surrounded by material that reflects radiation but does not emit it.

Let $g_{\mu\nu}$ and A_μ be the gravitational and electromagnetic potentials at the emitting surface. From a previous paper [4], the proper time interval for a displacement dx^μ at the emitting surface is

$$\begin{aligned} d\tau &= \frac{1}{c} [(g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{\rho'}{\rho c^2} A_\mu dx^\mu] \\ &= \frac{1}{c} (g_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu)^{\frac{1}{2}} + \frac{1}{\rho c^2} [\rho' A_4 - \frac{1}{c} \tilde{J} \cdot \tilde{A}] dt \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where ρ' is the scalar charge density, ρ is the scalar mass density, \tilde{J} is the 3-current density, c is the speed of light, and \tilde{A} is the 3 vector potential. For a first approximation it can be assumed that $\rho' A_4 = 0$, and that $g_{\mu\nu}$, ρ , \tilde{J} , and \tilde{A} are independent of time.

But $\frac{1}{2c} \tilde{J} \cdot \tilde{A}$ is the magnetic energy density. The magnetic energy density also has the form $\frac{B^2}{8\pi}$, where B is the magnitude of the magnetic field.

Let us define the gravitational redshift as

$$z_g = (g_{44})^{-\frac{1}{2}} - 1. \quad (2)$$

Then if z is the total redshift, it follows that [3]

$$\begin{aligned} B &\sim N^{\frac{1}{2}} \left[6.7 \times 10^{10} \left\{ \left(\frac{1}{z_g+1} - \frac{1}{z+1} \right) \right\}^{\frac{5}{4}} \right] \\ z &\sim \left[\frac{1}{z_g+1} - 1.5 \times 10^{-11} \left(\frac{B}{N^{\frac{1}{2}}} \right)^{\frac{4}{5}} \right]^{-1} - 1 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

For a neutron star we can assume $z_g=0.62$, [3] and then for the red shift of UHZ1 we get

$z = 10.1$, $z_g = 0.62$ and $N = 1$, which gives us $B \sim 1.53 \times 10^{13} \text{G}$. For a galaxy, z_g is very small [6] so let us assume that the z_g we need is 0. Then for the redshift of JADES-GS-z140-0 we get $z=14.32$, $z_g=0$ and $N=1$, which gives us $B \sim 3.13 \times 10^{13}$. Local magnetic fields of galaxies with neutron stars and magnetars can reach that level.

Another interesting fact is that for a galaxy with $z = \infty$ or cutoff we get $B \sim 3.41 \times 10^{13}$. So, it is reasonable to assume that for JADES-GS-z14-0 most of the emitting surface is cutoff and only a small part of the surface is emitting. One would certainly expect that B would be roughly constant over a small surface. This would explain the unusually narrow width of the spectral lines in JADES-GS-z14-0. [5]

References

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